

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TISSUE RESPONSE TECHNIQUE TO IMMEDIATE HYPOXIA: COMBINED USE OF CRYOLIPOLYSIS WITH CARBOXYTHERAPY IN THE FORMATION OF BEIGE ADIPOSE TISSUE AND ELIMINATION OF INFLAMMATORY FACTORS**¹Dr. Jairo Do Carmo Pirajá Junior, ²Dr. Carlos Ruiz Da Silva**¹Prof. Spec. PT, Dermatofunctional Physiotherapy Specialist. Faculdades Uninassau, Brasil).²Prof. Phd, Msc, PT, / Faculdade CTA- Brasil; College of Int. Medicine and Aesthetics Harold Gillies, USA.***Corresponding Author: Dr Jairo Do Carmo Pirajá Junior**

Prof. Spec. PT, Dermatofunctional Physiotherapy Specialist. Faculdades Uninassau, Brasil).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17472374>**How to cite this Article:** *Dr Jairo Do Carmo Pirajá Junior, Dr. Carlos Ruiz Da Silva. (2025). EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TISSUE RESPONSE TECHNIQUE TO IMMEDIATE HYPOXIA: COMBINED USE OF CRYOLIPOLYSIS WITH CARBOXYTHERAPY IN THE FORMATION OF BEIGE ADIPOSE TISSUE AND ELIMINATION OF INFLAMMATORY FACTORS. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(11), 182–199.

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Article Received on 25/09/2025

Article Revised on 15/10/2025

Article Published on 01/11/2025

ABSTRACT

Prolonged tissue hypoxia in mitochondrially deficient adipose tissue (white adipose tissue) is associated with several pathophysiological conditions, including chronic inflammation, obesity, microvascular complications, and diabetes. This prolonged oxygen (O₂) deficiency in adipose tissue creates a microenvironment that favors inflammation, increased ghrelin and hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF), decreased electrical conduction in sympathetic nerve endings, and initiates cell survival paradigms. Apoptosis-resistant factors (BCL1-XL and BCL2) prevail at the site. The induction of immediate hypoxia by freezing lipids through cryolipolysis, combined with elevated carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels, which also generate immediate hypoxia in adipose tissue, activates the apoptosis of deficient cells and shifts the tissue environment to "thrive mode," resulting in increased blood flow, O₂ supplementation, reduced inflammation, increased angiogenesis, mitochondrial crest formation, and activation of beige adipose tissue. Strategies using electrothermotherapy in aesthetics for body contouring increasingly incorporate systemic physiological manipulations combined with local application. In this study, in addition to demonstrating positive and impactful results with 100% satisfaction among those investigated, we demonstrated the true mechanism of action of these combinations through a literature review. The dual combination of cryolipolysis and carboxytherapy is effective and has already been used in more than 1,000 patients treated between 2022 and 2025, where the author uses the EUROICE terminology. The author explored a range of interventions designed to reduce visceral adipose tissue and prolonged inflammation, including cryolipolysis, carboxytherapy, and breathing exercises. The study involved 20 patients: 18 women and 2 men between the ages of 19 and 56, all with abdominal adipose tissue accumulation and hypotonia of the transverse muscle. An Immediate Hypoxia session was performed, followed by weekly sessions of 40 kHz ultrasound and functional electrical stimulation with breathing exercises. Before-and-after photographic comparisons of the protocol demonstrate visible and evident reductions in lipid deposits and correction of abdominal hypotonia. The treatment goes beyond aesthetic goals, offering a physiologically appropriate alternative for individuals unable to adhere to conventional training or surgical interventions. This treatment model promotes the transformation of white adipose tissue into beige adipose tissue and metabolic reprogramming, in addition to visible postural correction.

KEYWORDS: Cryolipolysis, Carboxytherapy, Body harmonization, weight loss, localized fat, low frequency ultrasound.

!-INTRODUCTION

Prolonged tissue hypoxia in mitochondrial-deficient adipose tissue (white adipose tissue) is associated with many pathophysiological conditions, including chronic inflammation, obesity, microvascular complications, and diabetes. This prolonged oxygen (O₂) deficiency in tissue assemblies creates a microenvironment that supports inflammation and initiates cellular survival paradigms. The induction of immediate hypoxia by freezing lipids through cryolipolysis, combined with elevated tissue carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels, activates apoptosis of deficient cells and shifts the tissue environment to "thrive mode," resulting in increased blood flow, added O₂, reduced inflammation, and increased angiogenesis (Ruiz-Silva, 2025).

Cardiovascular and microvascular diseases can be caused by the chronic interruption of normal blood flow, which causes previously healthy tissues to cascade into a serious and sometimes permanent pathological condition. The condition caused by sustained hypoxia results in a slower metabolism, dependent on glycolytic pathways, and a chronic inflammatory state, perpetuated by an increased production of hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF-1 α). Multiple transcriptional responses to HIF-1 α promote a survival response in cells, preventing cell death in response to continuous hypoxia (Kieras, 2021). In addition to cell survival, an important function of HIF-1 α is the transcriptional activation of genes involved in the growth of new blood vessels and new adipocytes in an attempt to reverse this condition.

In contrast to the survival mode induced by severe or chronic hypoxia, immediate or transient hypoxia caused by increased metabolic demand in tissues results in an acute decrease in ATP stores, which is detected by cells through the action of adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK) (Rodrigues, 2021). AMPK detects cellular energy status by monitoring the ATP:AMP ratio. When this ratio decreases, AMPK restores energy balance by inhibiting anabolic reactions that consume ATP and promoting catabolic processes that generate ATP. AMPK activation in vascular endothelial cells results in vasodilation and the growth of new blood vessels, increasing blood flow and oxygen delivery to the tissue, thus restoring normal tissue function (Rodrigues, 2021).

Tissue CO₂ levels immediately increase in response to increased metabolic demand. Elevated tissue CO₂ acts as a sensitive trigger for cellular responses to hypoxia, modulating biological signaling pathways (e.g., HIF-1 α and AMPK) to restore normal tissue function and homeostasis.

Adipose tissue deposition in specific anatomical regions remains a challenge in both metabolic regulation and aesthetic approaches. Lipogenesis, an enzyme-regulated anabolic process, converts excess energy substrates, such as glucose and free fatty acids, into triglycerides stored

in the cytoplasm of adipocytes. This mechanism, intensified by physical inactivity and hormonal imbalances, culminates in regional adipose tissue hypertrophy, often resistant to isolated caloric restriction or moderate aerobic activity (Lima; Vieira, 2017). Although often overlooked as aesthetic imperfections, these accumulations impact energy homeostasis and endocrine-metabolic function (Àvila, 2025).

Obesity and excess body fat have also been more recently associated with accelerated aging. In a study of over 1,000 people, obesity was found to increase biological age by up to 17% above chronological age (Correa-Burrows, 2022). Chronic inflammation associated with excess adipose tissue is believed to drive this increase in biological age, as chronic low-grade inflammation is a known hallmark of aging—one of the twelve cellular faults that accelerate the aging process (Franceschi, 2014; Loes-Otíz, 2023). In this study, those classified as obese also demonstrated evidence of other hallmarks of aging, including increased DNA damage and shorter telomeres (Correa-Burrows, 2022; Mundstock, 2015). Furthermore, several other studies have also demonstrated that obesity leads to other hallmarks of aging, including mitochondrial dysfunction (Tam, 2020), epigenetic alteration (Salvestrini, 2019), and senescence (Tam, 2020).

The weight-regulating hormone leptin is the antagonist of ghrelin, the orexigenic hormone that stimulates appetite. Research has shown that ghrelin-producing cells appear to be more abundant in morbidly obese and inflamed patients (Adamczak, 2013). Ghrelin is secreted in the stomach and inhibited by the satiety effects of leptin, which acts as a mechanism Hypothalamic-mediated feedback signaling. Intuitively, decreasing ghrelin and increasing leptin may be the apparent target of weight loss methods. However, there is a fine line between altering leptin/ghrelin concentrations and the hormonal imbalance that often precipitates weight gain. Unwarranted decreases in ghrelin and increases in leptin can also pose a health risk. Ghrelin is expressed in human T cells and monocytes to inhibit the expression of pro-inflammatory anorectic cytokines such as IL-1 β and IL-6, which are implicated in chronic low-grade inflammation and aging (Ershler and Keller, 2000; Dixit, 2004). The regulation of inflammatory cytokines by normal ghrelin levels may be crucial in preventing inflammation.

Preadipocytes that undergo excessive apoptosis as they differentiate acquire relative resistance to apoptosis (Sorisky, 2000). Inhibitors of apoptosis (IAPs) act by suppressing apoptosis by inhibiting caspase activity.

Extracellular survival factors inhibit apoptosis through several pathways and bind to cell surface receptors, suppressing apoptosis. They stimulate increased production of antiapoptotic Bcl2 proteins, such as Bcl2 and Bcl-XL, activated by multiple adipogenesis (Ruiz-

Silva, 2024). Injury to sympathetic innervation, the absence of axonal nerve transmission, causes injury and blockage of the electrical bioconductivity of the SNS, activating hyperplasia, especially after vacuum compression and massage after cryolipolysis (Jalin, 2020; Strounza, 2018). Stimulation of nerve endings in the sympathetic system is necessary to generate beige adipose tissue. With a transient decrease in sympathetic neural input, preadipocytes can be activated (Seaman, 2016; Ho, 2017). Excessively hypertrophic white adipose tissue undergoes continuous necrosis, activating transcription factors (PPAR gamma), causing adipocyte hyperplasia, which generates compression of sympathetic innervation, hypoxia, and continuous inflammation of the adipose tissue (Martins; Ruiz-Silva, 2022; Ruiz-Silva, 2022; 2023; 2023).

MICOS deficiency leads to a coarser inner membrane architecture, and these mutations affect MICOS function and are responsible for a diverse spectrum of human diseases (Ruiz-Silva, 2023). Adipose tissue reduction is energy-dependent and can be achieved by reducing fat stores (lipolysis) or by permanent removal of adipocytes, necrosis, and apoptosis. Lipolysis is a metabolic process that degrades triglycerides present in adipose cells into their constituent molecules, glycerol and free fatty acids (FFA), through hydrolysis. (Ruiz-Silva, 2023; 2024).

Human brown adipocytes possess molecular attributes such as constitutive expression of UCP1, homogeneous multilocular morphology, and myogenic origin (Myf5+), while beige adipose tissue arises from non-myogenic progenitors (Myf52) under environmental stimuli, such as cold and exercise, and exhibits low levels of UCP1 expression under unstimulated conditions (Okla, 2017). Studies conducted by Dr. Loop between 2013 and 2016 demonstrated that cold exposure and exercise increase levels of the hormones irisin (produced by muscle) and FGF21 (produced by brown fat). In the laboratory, irisin and FGF21 can differentiate cells into beige adipose tissue cells over a six-day period (Loop, 2018). These two hormones, irisin and FGF21, are the primary signals that stimulate energy expenditure in the laboratory. Recent research suggests an inverse association between BMI and plasma irisin concentrations in morbidly obese individuals. In mammals, UCP1 BAT provides the primary mechanism for adaptive non-shivering thermogenesis to maintain body temperature in cold environments.

The use of cryolipolysis combined with microcurrents in the electrolipolysis mode

For transcriptional activation of UCP1, several transcriptional and co-regulatory factors are required, including PPARs and PGC1 α (Dempersmier, 2015; Kelpert, 2017). However, the temperature range used to assess cold-induced thermogenesis represents another source of variability. The concept of cryoexposure is the use of local tissue cooling to control obesity. In cryolipolysis, apoptosis (hypoxia and reperfusion) is

observed, with losses recorded over a long period (Manstein, 2008; 2009; Pugliese, 2020; Zelickson, 2009). Cryoexposure is a controlled method that uses cooling to induce lipolysis without inflammation (controlled by biochemical tests), a result generated by adaptive cryothermogenesis (Loop, 2018; 2022).

Exposure to environmental cold leads to a decrease in adipose tissue. When exposed to low temperatures, homeothermic mechanisms in humans include increased skin vasoconstriction to reduce heat loss and increased endogenous heat production, triggered by an increase in basal metabolic rate. Cold exposure also causes skeletal muscles to produce heat through muscle shivering-independent thermogenesis, while muscle shivering-independent thermogenesis occurs in brown adipose tissue (BAT). Although the hypothesis of using cold exposure as a weight loss strategy was abandoned due to the belief that humans lacked brown adipose tissue, studies have shown that humans possess significant amounts of brown fat deposits, and the browning process can be stimulated by β 3-AR receptor agonists (Ikeda, 2020).

Loop's recent publication brought to light the concept of weight loss with cryoexposure, based on the hypothesis of white fat conversion to brown tissue, which dates back over a century (Loop, 2018). Cold exposure increases energy and caloric expenditure through thermogenesis and fat metabolism (Loop, 2018). Despite the previous belief that brown adipose tissue was absent in humans, fluorodeoxyglucose imaging has shown the presence of large expansions of brown fat deposits (Loop, 2018). Evidence suggests that the conversion of white tissue to brown tissue is possible through the activation of BAT genes by transcription factors (Dempersmier, 2015). Daily serial cooling of abdominal adipose tissue results in progressive adipose tissue loss, confirmed by dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry, with no evidence of systemic inflammation, abnormal fat mobilization, or disruption of cellular integrity, necrosis, or death (Loop, 2018). Cryoexposure has been shown to reduce circumference and BMI without affecting inflammatory biomarkers, allowing daily applications (Loop, 2018). Lipid profile markers, including total cholesterol (TC), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), alanine aminotransferase (ALAT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), gamma-glutamyltransferase (GGT), triglycerides (TG) and their relevant ratios, as well as thyroid hormones (TSH, total T4, and free T4), were also analyzed (Loop, 2018). Each cryoexposure application results in the extraction of 1,330 kcal via thermogenesis, as reported by Yoneshiro, Lans, and Le in 2013 (Loop, 2018). Cold-induced upregulation of UCP-1 O516 ZFP factors in low-temperature fat cells generates thermogenesis, allowing mitochondria to metabolize fat by beta-oxidation and generate heat (Dempersmier, 2015). Cold exposure also increases the expression of metabolic activity in beige tissue, leading to increased expression of the UCP-1

protein, which promotes thermogenesis and heat generation (Ikeda, 2020). The key to maximizing the effects of cryoexposure is to freeze as many areas as possible simultaneously and stimulate sympathetic nervous system receptors through electrolipolysis or electrostimulation to induce Zfp516 expression through sympathetic stimulation (contraction) by cold. Zfp516 binds to the PGC1 α and Cox promoter regions, promoting transcriptional activation (Dempersmier, 2015). Intense contractions increase the expression of signaling proteins such as PPAR γ PGC-1 α , which regulates mitochondrial biogenesis. Supramaximal contractions above 10 Hz and high magnetic flux density are most effective in activating PGC1 α and inducing browning. These contractions stimulate anaerobic muscle fibers to undergo repetitive contractions, leading to high energy demand and a subsequent shift from aerobic to anaerobic metabolism. Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma-1 alpha (PGC1-alpha) is a transcriptional coactivator that plays a critical role in regulating energy metabolism and thermogenesis.

One of its primary its main functions are to induce browning of white adipose tissue (WAT), promoting the conversion of white adipocytes to brown adipocytes. This transformation involves the activation of thermogenesis mediated by uncoupling protein 1 (UCP1), which generates heat and increases metabolic activity in brown adipocytes.

The combination of cold and sympathetic nervous system stimulation through electrotherapy promotes the activation of the PERK and MICUS systems. The freezing action and simulation of physical activity through microcurrent (release of hormones similar to physical activity) after lipolytic stimuli (electrolipolysis) encounters an environment with many lipid droplets that influence the organization of cristae; mitochondria perform β -oxidation of fatty acids, but when stimulated by cold, drastic changes in morphology occur due to the activation of PERK (Gallardo-Montejano, 2021).

Cryolipolysis promotes the selective reduction of adipose cells. Histological analysis confirmed a selective and gradual reduction of adipose tissue through programmed death (apoptosis) triggered by reperfusion, the return of blood to the tissue by hypoxia activated by lipid freezing. The method's safety is highlighted by the absence of significant increases in liver enzymes or serum lipids (Ruiz-Silva, 2025).

Molecular studies demonstrated no changes in peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR) transcripts. No changes in these transcripts were observed, highlighting the safety of the technology used (Ferraro, 2012).

Several physiological factors, such as temperature and exercise, have been shown to regulate the browning process. Maximal muscle contractions have been shown

to activate PGC1-alpha, leading to increased mitochondrial biogenesis and oxidative metabolism. Maximal contractions cause a rapid and sustained increase in intracellular calcium levels, which activates calcium-dependent calmodulin kinase (CaMK); CaMK, in turn, phosphorylates PGC1-alpha. Maximal contractions promote the release of lactate and other metabolic intermediates that can activate AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), a key regulator of energy homeostasis that also activates PGC1-alpha.

Performing maximal contractions in environments with temperatures close to 0°C has been shown to be more effective in inducing browning compared to performing these contractions at room temperature. This is because cold exposure can activate the sympathetic nervous system and increase the secretion of norepinephrine, a hormone that stimulates lipolysis and activates mitochondrial thermogenesis, through the activation of β 3-adrenergic receptors. Activation of β 3-adrenergic receptors leads to the activation of AMPK, which in turn phosphorylates and activates PGC1-alpha. PGC1-alpha induces the expression of genes involved in mitochondrial biogenesis and oxidative metabolism, leading to an increase in mitochondrial thermogenesis and energy expenditure. In addition to its effects on thermogenesis, cold exposure can also activate the transient receptor potential cation channel member V, subfamily 1 (TRPV1), which is sensitive to low temperatures and is expressed in sensory neurons and adipose tissue. TRPV1 activation leads to the secretion of neuropeptide Y (NPY) and agouti-related protein (AgRP), two neuropeptides that stimulate food intake and reduce energy expenditure. However, TRPV1 activation in adipose tissue can also lead to the activation of mitochondrial thermogenesis through the activation of sympathetic nerves and the secretion of norepinephrine. In summary, performing submaximal and maximal contractions in environments with temperatures close to 0°C is more efficient in inducing browning than at room temperature, due to the activation of the sympathetic nervous system and the increased concentration of norepinephrine, which promotes the activation of MTD thermogenesis through the activation of β 3-adrenergic receptors and the activation of PGC-1 α . Furthermore, cold exposure can also activate the transient receptor potential subfamily V member 1 (TRPV1) cation channel, leading to the production of neuropeptides that stimulate food intake and produce energy expenditure.

Carboxytherapy Physiological Basis

Despite several publications demonstrating the effectiveness of carboxytherapy in reducing adipose tissue (Santos et al, 2020; Zago, 2020; Kill, 2020; Borba, 2021; Bastos, 2020; Alves, 2018; Moreira, 2020; Monteiro, 2021; Marinho, 2021; Lee, 2016; Kroumpouza, 2022; Kolodziejczak, 2018), none demonstrate the actual physiology capable of generating lipolysis. According to Milani, 2020, carboxytherapy is an invasive technique that uses medicinal carbon dioxide

(CO₂), which is injected with an insulin needle into the subcutaneous tissue to stimulate physiological effects to improve circulation and tissue oxygenation. The Bohr effect is the main effect of carboxytherapy, as it acts on the vascular microcirculation of connective tissue, thus promoting vasodilation and increased neovascular drainage (Reis et al, 2018; Farina et al, 2020). After a literature review, we conclude that CO₂ activates angiogenesis not mediated by hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α ; CO₂ is strongly anti-inflammatory; CO₂ inhibits tumor growth and metastasis; and CO₂ can stimulate the same pathways as exercise and, therefore, acts as a critical mediator in the biological response of skeletal muscle to tissue hypoxia.

This review presents data that highlight the potential use of CO₂ as a therapeutic approach for tissue hypoxia, promoting tissue repair, reducing inflammation, reversing the pathophysiological effects of hyperglycemia, and generating lipolysis. Furthermore, it summarizes the state of knowledge regarding the cellular and molecular mechanisms underlying these beneficial effects of therapeutic CO₂ administration.

In addition to its regenerative effects, CO₂ has anti-inflammatory effects (Hanly, 2006; Howar, 1993). The key to the anti-inflammatory response using CO₂ is the fact that it can penetrate and act directly on cells to modulate intracellular pathways that lead to inflammation and oxidative stress, as well as pathways linked to cell survival, proliferation, and apoptosis (Contreras, 2015). It is also relevant for patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), in which the viral spike protein of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) binds to and disrupts the function of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) on cell surfaces, leading to the activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs) and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., interferon-gamma, IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α) that cause pneumonia or ARDS (Galganska, 2021). Mechanisms of Action of Carbon Dioxide Therapy.

CO₂/H⁺ concentrations and carbonic anhydrase govern CO₂ sensing in the regulation of cellular function, with many of the findings relying on CO₂ hydration and proton production to activate sensors and initiate a response. While hydration occurs spontaneously under physiological conditions, it occurs up to six orders of magnitude faster in the presence of the enzyme carbonic anhydrase (CA).^[48] CO₂ hydration through the action of CA is an important pathway for many responses. Although the relative importance of protons and CA is discussed in the context of the effect of CO₂ on O₂ release from hemoglobin in red blood cells, there are many additional responses where hydration is noted. The fact that it is not discussed does not mean that protons are unimportant. The role of protons is complicated by

the fact that CO₂ can affect protons extracellularly independently of how it affects protons intracellularly, indicating the importance of CA location. As more is discovered about the biology of CO₂, the relative importance of protons and CA in sensing CO₂ levels will come to light.

Increasing Blood Flow and Tissue Oxygenation

Increasing the CO₂ concentration in tissue increases blood flow to that tissue (Xu, 2018; Matsumoto, 2016), and increased blood flow stimulates flow-mediated dilation of blood vessels (Ogoh, 2016; Hill, 2021). This vasodilatory action is partly due to CO₂-induced NO production by the endothelium (which acts through the activation of cyclic GMP to relax the underlying smooth muscle), as it can be attenuated by inhibition of the endothelial NO synthase enzyme (Minamiyama, 2010).

An alternative mechanism for CO₂-mediated increases in blood flow involves connexins and ATP release, which may act on ATP-sensitive potassium (K_{ATP}) channels in vascular smooth muscle to cause vasodilation, contributing to both resting blood flow and vasodilator-induced increases in blood flow. Connexins form large-pore channels that function as dodecameric gap junctions or hexameric hemichannels to allow the regulated movement of small molecules and ions across cell membranes. Hemichannels are a particularly important mechanism for ATP release in extracellular space (Dospinesw, 2019). CO₂ binds to a carbamylation motif in connexins Cx26, Cx30, and Cx32, causing their hemichannels to open. Fluctuations in CO₂ levels within the tissue alter their opening probability (Hill, 2016). Although direct CO₂-dependent opening of the Cx26 hemichannel and subsequent ATP release have been shown to mediate an important part of neurovascular coupling (Hosford, 2022), it is possible that CO₂ binding to endothelial Cx32 may explain the release of ATP into the blood in skeletal muscle during exercise, as the source of ATP remains to be defined (Kirby, 2013). CO₂-mediated CGRP release and CA-dependent proton production can also activate K_{ATP} channels in vascular smooth muscle (Brayden, 2002; Davies, 1990).

Finally, it has been demonstrated in the human forearm that there is an increased release of O₂ from hemoglobin when CO₂ is applied to the skin (TD) (Sakai, 2011). This CO₂-driven elevation in tissue oxygenation can be explained by the Bohr effect, a rightward shift of the O₂-hemoglobin dissociation curve with an increase in pCO₂ or a decrease in pH (Bohr, 1904). This relationship was discovered in 1904 by Christian Bohr (Bohr, 1904), who showed that increasing CO₂ tensions decreased the O₂ affinity of whole blood in dogs. It should be noted, however, that Malte et al. showed that protons generated by CA have a greater effect on O₂ binding to hemoglobin than CO₂ itself (Figure 1) (Malte, 2018).

Figure 1. The Bohr effect as defined by CO₂ and protons. The Bohr and Haldane effects were modeled to describe the interactions between O₂ and CO₂ binding to hemoglobin (Malte, 2018). The Bohr effect describes how O₂ binding is decreased in the presence of CO₂ and protons. Graph (A) shows the traditional oxygen equilibrium curves (A) modeled under different CO₂ levels. The three black curves are the oxygen equilibrium curves obtained when the CO₂ partial pressure is held constant at the indicated values. The blue curve is obtained when CO₂ is added while oxygen is removed at a gas exchange rate, respiratory quotient (RQ), of 0.83. Graph (B) shows the effect of protons (B) on binding with a constant PCO₂ value of 40 mmHg and pH 7.2 at a PO₂ of 100 mmHg. Protons bind to Bohr groups on hemoglobin. The five oxygen equilibrium curves are obtained by increasing the number of bound Bohr groups (i.e., bound protons), as indicated by the numbers on the curves. pH is not shown because it is a poor indicator of proton binding. As protons bind to hemoglobin, pH increases. Figures reprinted/adapted with permission from Ref. (Malte, 2018). Copyright 2018, Journal of Applied Physiology.

There are two Bohr groups in each portion of hemoglobin, allowing a total of eight protons to interact with the hemoglobin molecule. In red blood cells, CO₂ is rapidly interconverted into HCO₃⁻ and H⁺ ions via CA to generate the protons that can cause this effect. In the absence of CO₂ and protons, hemoglobin will bind O₂ until it reaches essentially anoxic tissue. Thus, tissues with low metabolism or that may be exposed to the body surface will have low CO₂ levels and, therefore, will receive little O₂ from the blood that may be flowing through the tissue. Raising CO₂ to generate protons will force a rightward shift in the curves, so that O₂ is released from hemoglobin and delivered to the tissue [Graph A]. The rightward shift caused by CO₂ alone is relatively limited.

When external CO₂ is applied, the CO₂ is hydrated in the presence of CA, producing higher proton concentrations. The rapid hydration of CO₂ maintains the driving force for CO₂ diffusion into red blood cells and prevents CO₂ loss through conversion to HCO₂⁻. The effect of protons on oxygen binding is drastic, decreasing oxygen binding, as shown in Graph B. When hemoglobin binds protons during oxygen release, it acts as a buffer. The pH actually increases, so red blood cell pH is not a good indicator of proton binding to hemoglobin. According to Malte and Lykkeboe, "The Bohr effect is exerted by protons preloaded on Bohr groups at a given pH, as well as protons absorbed by Bohr groups during gas exchange. The proton preload sets the oxygen affinity (i.e., P₅₀) at the onset of gas exchange. The protons absorbed during gas exchange lead to a further progressive decrease in oxygen affinity.

The concerted effect of these two processes is very large, and the size of the Bohr effect has a direct influence on the oxygen affinity of hemoglobin." (Malte, 2018).

Enhancing Angiogenesis

While a single CO₂ treatment can stimulate vasodilation and increase the release of O₂ from hemoglobin due to the Bohr effect, repeated applications of CO₂ maintain the tissue's O₂ supply and induce angiogenesis (Xu, 2018; Xu 2017). Responses to CO₂ include increases in basic fibroblast growth factor (Reglin, 2014; Nemeth, 2018), VEGF (Xu, 2018; Xu 2017), SIRT1 (Oe, 2018), PGC-1 α (Wollina, 2004; Macura, 2020; Izumi, 2015; Irie, 2005), and NO (Xu, 2018; Xu 2017), all linked to neovascularization. Angiogenesis is a critical part of the healing process and is known to occur in response to tissue hypoxia. Hypoxia induces the transcription of angiogenic genes, such as VEGF, in part by stabilizing hypoxia-inducible transcription factors (Ferrara, 2003). A deficiency in blood flow leads to hypoxia, and elevated levels of CO₂ accumulate in the tissue. Interestingly, although therapeutic CO₂ introduction causes angiogenesis, it decreases or prevents HIF-1 α production (Selfridged, 2016; Takemori, 2016). One mechanism for CO₂-mediated HIF-1 α suppression is through pH-dependent and O₂-independent HIF-1 α degradation.

Similarly, a non-HIF-mediated process can occur in skeletal muscle in response to exercise. Exercise generates high CO₂ concentrations in skeletal muscle, and CO₂ stimulates PGC-1 α (Colfrey, 2016). PGC-1 α is a hypoxia-induced metabolic sensor that regulates VEGF expression and angiogenesis in cultured muscle cells and

skeletal muscle *in vivo* (Arany, 2018). PGC-1 α promotes angiogenesis through interaction with estrogen-related receptor alpha (ERR α), an orphan nuclear receptor that binds to the promoter region and a novel enhancer in the first intron of the VEGF gene to initiate robust VEGF gene activation in a HIF-independent manner (Arany, 2018; Hass, 2012; Yan, 2011). A reduced increase in VEGF expression in PGC-1 α knockout mice after exercise demonstrates the functional relevance of this non-HIF-1 α pathway in coordinating the angiogenic response to exercise (Hass, 2012).

The CO₂ sensor that triggers the angiogenic process has not yet been defined. It was recently demonstrated that connexins bind CO₂ (Dospinescu, 2019). Cx32 is expressed in endothelial cells and regulates angiogenesis, increasing tube formation and cell migration (Okamoto, 2004). It is conceivable that CO₂ binding to Cx32 initiates neovascularization in response to chronic tissue hypoxia. An alternative candidate for a tissue CO₂ sensor is ubiquitin. Although much of the control of angiogenic events is instigated by hypoxia-induced VEGF expression, the ubiquitin-proteasome system plays a central role in fine-tuning the functions of key proangiogenic proteins, including VEGF, VEGF receptors, angiogenic signaling proteins, and other non-VEGF pathways (Hahini, 2012). Ubiquitin is a highly conserved protein that regulates both protein activity and protein degradation through conjugation with target proteins (Hahini, 2012; Linthwaite, 2021). CO₂ binds to lysine residues in ubiquitin, forming carbamate, and this reversible carbamylation reaction may be involved in the diverse physiological responses to fluctuating pCO₂ levels. Linthwaite et al. described several sites where CO₂ could bind to ubiquitin and alter its properties (Linthwaite, 2021). Deng et al. described how deubiquitination of AMPK is critical for its activation (Deng, 2016). AMPK is a crucial cellular energy sensor and is activated when intracellular ATP concentrations decrease and AMP or ADP concentrations increase in response to energetic or pathological stresses (Haldiez, 2012). AMPK activation plays a critical role in PGC-1 α activation and therefore may be the link between CO₂ and exercise to initiate non-HIF-mediated angiogenesis (Yan, 2011).

Reducing Inflammation

Some of the beneficial effects of therapeutic CO₂ may be related to its ability to suppress inflammatory signaling and increase ROS. Hypoxia, HIF-1 α , and increased expression of glycolytic enzymes are associated with inflammation, and NF- κ B can lead to increased HIF-1 α expression. The loss of oxygen supply, energy depletion, and increased oxidative stress in ischemia/hypoxia result in reduced ATP synthesis and initiate a cascade of pathways that lead to cell death if not reversed. SIRT1 plays an important role in protecting against cellular stress and controlling metabolic pathways during ischemia/hypoxia.

CO₂ can trigger a specific repertoire of transcriptional events in a dose-dependent manner (Cummins, 2010). NF- κ B is the master regulator of the sensing and signaling pathways that induce the transcription of multiple pro-inflammatory genes. As described in the studies mentioned above and others (Hanly, 2006; Cummins, 2010), CO₂ can counteract inflammation to restore homeostasis. CO₂ interrupts inflammation by binding to ubiquitin. Once CO₂ is bound, ubiquitin will remodel and transform into a proteasome that will directly decrease the NF- κ B response (Linthwaite, 2021; Keogh, 2017). During deubiquitination, ubiquitin is removed from a substrate to release its activity. This has been described as CO₂-induced NFKB deactivation (Keogh, 2017). Adenyl cyclase stimulation: CO₂ infusion into the subcutaneous tissue leads to a local increase in gas, which activates the enzyme adenyl cyclase. Increased cAMP: Activated adenyl cyclase generates an increase in the intracellular concentration of cAMP. Adipocyte lysis: The increase in cAMP initiates the lysis of triglycerides stored within the adipocyte, releasing free fatty acids and glycerol into the bloodstream. This process is known as lipolysis.

Carbon dioxide (CO₂), used in the procedure, reacts with factors regulating tissue perfusion under physiological conditions. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is formed within cells as a result of cellular metabolism and then diffuses out of the cell. As a result, CO₂ affects microcirculation in arterioles and precapillary vessels. As a result, tissue blood flow increases (KOŁODZIEJCZAK et al., 2018). In adipose tissue, carbon dioxide (CO₂) activates adenyl cyclase. Furthermore, the effects of CO₂ on adipose tissue can be direct or indirect. When carbon dioxide (CO₂) has a direct lipolytic effect, there is a mechanical action mediated by the flow of gas injected into the hypodermis, without harming other tissues. The indirect effect of CO₂ is related to the gas's ability to increase oxygen bioavailability for adipocyte metabolic activities, including fatty acid oxidative processes, reducing oxygen affinity for hemoglobin (DESSY, 2016).

II - MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fifteen patients of both sexes, aged between 25 and 50, were treated. They were diagnosed with excess abdominal adipose tissue and sagging abdominal muscles, especially the transversus abdominis muscle. All patients had clinical indications for cryolipolysis combined with microcurrent therapy, in addition to carboxytherapy. All patients were duly informed with the Informed Consent Form and signed an authorization for the use of their images, which was completed for diagnostic, scientific, and educational purposes.

Treatment performed

1. Cleansing the area to be treated with 2% aqueous chlorhexidine.
2. Use of an antifreeze blanket with a protective liner.
3. Use of microcurrents at 10 Hz with an intensity of 700 au.

4. Cryolipolysis freezing for 30 minutes at -11 degrees Celsius with a second 15-minute cooling cycle.
5. Use of 40 kHz ultrasound at 3.0 watts cm², 2 minutes per head area, on all frozen tissue.
6. Finalization with Carboxytherapy, inflating the entire frozen area.

Weekly treatments were performed with 40 kHz ultrasound and functional electrostimulation combined with respiratory exercises for the transverse muscles.

III. RESULTS

Figures 2 to 16 show clinical cases treated with the protocol described above.

Figure 2: Patient J.F, Female, 40 years old.

Figure 3: Patient R.T.S J.F, male, 35 years old.

Figure 4: Patient M.A.S, female, 56 years old.

Figure 5: Patient R.F, female, 45 years old.

Figure 6: Patient L.S, female, 19 years old.

Figure 7: Patient A.F.J, female, 56 years old.

Figure 8: Patient S.F.A, female, 30 years old.

IV- DISCUSSION

Visual comparisons between pre- and post-intervention photographic records reveal evident reductions in subcutaneous fat volume, and a decrease in initial muscle hypotonia demonstrates extraordinary improvements in abdominal contour and skin tension, reporting complete satisfaction with the results. These results reflect not only apoptosis and reduction of local adipose tissue, but also the systemic metabolic reorientation promoted by the technique of immediate hypoxia and hyperoxygenation

with CO₂, followed by a program of active muscle contraction and electrically induced muscle contraction. Previous reports identify the activation of AMPK triggered by FES and the subsequent mobilization of GLUT-4 as central processes in the increase in insulin-independent glucose uptake and fatty acid oxidation (Paul 2009), mechanisms likely replicated in this group.

The photographic documentation shows patients before the intervention, demonstrating a concentration of

adipose tissue in the infra- and supra-umbilical regions, as well as abdominal protrusion resulting from muscle hypotonia. Eight weeks after treatment, a reduction in subcutaneous volume, improvement in abdominal contour, and improved postural alignment were observed. The postural correction achieved in hypotonic individuals indicates that the respiratory and electrostimulation technique acts beyond acetylcholine metabolism and energy expenditure. By recruiting the deep transverse muscles, it promotes trunk stability and reduces abdominal protrusion, often misinterpreted as fat accumulation.

The results of the application of Cryolipolysis and Carboxytherapy using the immediate hypoxia technique induced with weekly low-frequency ultrasound treatments, followed by electrostimulation-assisted transverse muscle exercises, show consistent adipocyte attenuation. The effect of apoptosis initially generated by the hypoxia of Cryolipolysis, leading to the abandonment of mitochondrial cytochrome C and activation of procaspases 8 and 9, and inhibition of PPAR via the application of Carboxytherapy and potentiated by low-frequency ultrasound, this effect is consistent with the stimulation of apoptosis by low-frequency ultrasound previously described in controlled *ex vivo* models (Palumbo, 2011) and *in vivo* (Avila; Ruiz-Silva, 2025). Current visual evidence, although lacking histological verification, aligns with the expected morphological patterns of post-apoptosis body remodeling: smoother transitions between tissue planes, reduced bulging, and decreased localized lipid accumulation. These changes, which were far superior to surgical interventions and restrictive diets, suggest that mechanical fragmentation occurs at the cellular level, without visible inflammation or dermal compromise. In all 15 cases evaluated, volumetric reduction occurred without any recorded adverse cutaneous or circulatory effects.

Although the photographic method does not provide metric precision, the repeatability of visual results strengthens interpretive reliability (Ruiz-Silva, 2025).

Comparative studies corroborate the methodological framework for the use of cryolipolysis for adipose tissue reduction and weight loss (Ruiz-Silva, 2025). Pugliese *et al.* (2013) describe the occurrence of apoptosis after histological examination of adipocyte membranes under similar sonic protocols, while Honda *et al.* (2016) associate the use of 40 kHz ultrasound with a transient increase in free fatty acids (NEFA) without altering the lipid profile. These parallel findings corroborate the hypothesis that controlled ultrasound lysis promotes adipose apoptosis within physiological limits. Current clinical observations corroborate these conclusions. The intervention can affect metabolic flexibility, adipokine expression, and regional thermogenesis.

Functional electrical stimulation (FES), by inducing artificial muscle contractions, generates systemic

biochemical effects. During contraction, AMPK, an enzyme sensitive to energy depletion, is activated, allowing the translocation of glucose transporters independently of insulin. Concomitantly, irisin, a myokine encoded by FNDC5, is released. Its action induces the phenotypic conversion of white adipocytes to beige cells via UCP1 expression, which intensifies thermogenesis and calorie expenditure (Pauli, 2009; Ruiz-Silva, 2023). Thus, FES ceases to be a mere toning tool and begins to act as a metabolic modulator (Ruiz-Silva, 2025).

Localized application of FES in areas of hypotonia, such as the abdomen, combined with specific breathing exercises for the transverse musculature, offers complementary responses. In muscles with low basal activation, electrical stimulation increases regional perfusion and promotes the oxidative use of fatty acids released by lipolysis (Martins, 2021). This metabolic redistribution supports the inclusion of FES in body contouring protocols, especially in patients individuals with restrictions on conventional exercise due to musculoskeletal limitations or chronic clinical conditions (Avila; Ruiz-Silva, 2025).

Immediate and transient hypoxia induction techniques with cryolipolysis and carboxytherapy, combined with beta-adrenergic stimulation, promote the biogenesis of mitochondrial cristae. Beige adipose tissue is a game-changer in the treatment of obesity and comorbidities due to its thermogenic and neurogenic effects (Martins; Ruiz-Silva, 2021; Ruiz-Silva, 2023; Ruiz-Silva, 2024). Cold stress or beta-adrenergic stimulation activates PERK, which phosphorylates N-acetylglucosamine transferase (OGT). OGT phosphorylates TOM70 at Ser94, increasing the import of the MIC19 protein into mitochondria, promoting cristae formation and respiration. This activates the transformation of white adipose tissue (rich in lipids and poor in mitochondria) into beige adipose tissue (poor in lipids and rich in mitochondria) (Ruiz-Silva; 2024).

The endoplasmic reticulum (ER) kinase PERK is extremely sensitive to cold stress and stimuli from sympathetic nervous system (SNS), promoting the formation of mitochondrial cristae through increased mitochondrial import of MIC19, aided by TOM70 (Ruiz-Silva, 2023; 2024). Through cryolipolysis, the proliferation of healthy mitochondria is activated without the predominance of survival factors with anti-apoptosis proteins, through the mobile loop of cryolipolysis, generating the activation of the cristae organizing system MICOS through the translocation of the outer membrane translocation receptors MIC19 and 70. Beta-adrenergic stimuli also promote cristae biogenesis. The key is to alter this mitochondrial characteristic through fission (Yau, 2020; Martins; Ruiz-Silva, 2021; Ruiz-Silva, 2023; 2023). The combination of cold with sympathetic nervous system stimulation through electrotherapy promotes the activation of the PERK and MICOS. The

freezing action and simulation of physical activity through microcurrents (release of hormones similar to physical activity) after lipolytic stimuli (electrolipolysis) encounters an environment with many lipid droplets that influence cristae organization. Mitochondria perform the β -oxidation of fatty acids; however, when stimulated by cold, drastic changes in morphology occur due to the activation of PERK. (Gallardo-Montejano, 2021)

Crystal density increased dramatically after cold exposure, forcing the overexpression of perilipin 5 (PLIN5). This increase in cristae density may be caused by PERK-dependent ER stress (Latorre-Muro *et al.*, 2021).

Microcurrents or TCM, Cellular Microtherapy, consist of the application of low-intensity (μ A) and low-frequency currents, similar to the endogenous electric fields generated during tissue repair systems (Ruiz-Silva, 2006; 2016; Xu, 2021) Microcurrent compensates for the bioelectricity that is decreased in hypoxic and inflamed tissues (Ruiz-Silva, 2006; 2016; Xu, 2021; Coy, 2022), generating ATP and mitogenesis. The presence of microcurrent generates a constant intensity current, increasing electrical flow, dissociating the water molecule, and forming hydrogen and hydroxyl ions around both electrodes. Hydrogen leads to the creation of ATP. It follows that, as a residual effect after the microcurrent stimulator is turned off, ATP production continues at the site. This ATP formation can be explained by Mitchell's chemiosmotic theory (Cheng, 1985; Ruiz-Silva, 2016).

Ruiz-Silva demonstrated that the number of superficial inflammatory cells decreased with increasing intensity of the applied low-frequency microcurrent, finding a statistically significant effect on the induction of lipolysis through stimulation of the postganglionic sympathetic neuron (Vilarinho *et al.* 2022; Couto; Ruiz-Silva; 2010).

The main purpose of the SNS is to stimulate the body's fight-or-flight response, remaining constantly active to maintain homeostasis (Motiejunaite *et al.*, 2021). Microcurrent stimulation exerts "hormone-like effects," such as the secretion of norepinephrine in the postganglionic sympathetic neuron of the nervous system and in the G protein of the cell membrane (Al-Tubaikh, 2018). Norepinephrine secretion increases by binding to the β 3-adrenoreceptor (β 3-AR), which in turn converts ATP to cAMP in adipocytes (Noites, 2017).

The immediate hypoxia technique aims to reverse the effects of prolonged tissue hypoxia in adipose tissue with mitochondrial deficiency (white adipose tissue), reversing the pathological picture that includes chronic inflammation, obesity, microvascular complications, and diabetes. Using the immediate hypoxia and hyperoxygenation technique, we correct prolonged oxygen (O_2) deficiency and inhibit cell survival factors.

In addition to cell survival, an important function of HIF-1 α is the transcriptional activation of genes involved in the growth of new adipocytes. With the neovascularization promoted by this technique, we improve blood flow to supply more O_2 to the tissue and reverse hypoxia, while activating the bioconductivity of the sympathetic nervous system.

In contrast to the survival mode induced by severe or chronic hypoxia, limited or transient hypoxia caused by increased metabolic demand in tissues results in an acute decrease in ATP stores, which is detected by cells through the action of adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK). AMPK detects cellular energy status by monitoring the ATP:AMP ratio. When this ratio decreases, AMPK restores energy balance by inhibiting anabolic reactions that consume ATP and promoting catabolic processes that generate ATP. Activation of AMPK in vascular endothelial cells results in vasodilation and the growth of new blood vessels, increasing blood flow and oxygen supply to the tissue, thus restoring normal tissue function (Rodriguez, 2021).

The induction of immediate hypoxia by freezing lipids through cryolipolysis, combined with elevated tissue carbon dioxide (CO_2) levels, activates apoptosis of deficient cells and shifts the tissue environment to "thriving mode," resulting in increased blood flow, oxygen supply, reduced inflammation, and increased angiogenesis and mitochondria. This study demonstrated efficacy in the 20 patients treated.

V- CONCLUSION

The induction of immediate hypoxia by freezing lipids through cryolipolysis, combined with high levels of carbon dioxide (CO_2) in the tissues, activates the apoptosis of deficient cells and generates a shift in the inflamed tissue environment, with mitochondrial deficiency and low blood circulation, to "thriving mode," resulting in increased blood flow, added O_2 , reduced inflammation, and increased angiogenesis and mitochondrial crest formation, generating beige adipose tissue.

Freezing at low temperatures generates immediate hypoxia, initiating the apoptosis process by initiating the cytochrome c release cascade from the mitochondria and activating pro-apoptotic BH 123. Upon removal of the plaques, blood returns, which is blood reperfusion in the adipocytes, generating reactive oxygen species (oxidation) and activating apoptosis via the death receptor TNF α . Cryolipolysis promotes the selective reduction of adipose cells and is effective in treating dermal collagen remodeling. Concomitant with this effect, PERK is activated, which phosphorylates N-acetylglucosamine transferase (OGT), phosphorylating TOM70 at Ser94, increasing the import of the MIC19 protein into the mitochondria and promoting the formation of cristae and the formation of beige adipose tissue, rich in UCP1. Combined with CO_2 infusion, in

addition to a new immediate hypoxia, we activate the inhibition of transcription factors, PPAR γ , and generate a change in adipocyte typology, starting with the mitochondria and their organelles responsible for inhibiting apoptosis.

Strategies using electrothermotherapy in aesthetics for body contouring increasingly incorporate systemic physiological manipulations associated with local application. In this study, in addition to demonstrating positive and impactful results with 100% satisfaction among those investigated, we demonstrated the true mechanism of action of these combinations through a literature review.

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